

Clearing the sky from the clouds – The Mineral Intelligence Capacity Analysis (MICA) project

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MICA develops the EU-RMICP with an innovative visualization interface that guides the user to a 'recipe' for how to find answers to particular mineral raw material related questions. This is different from a database providing pre-formulated answers to questions: MICA offers an expert-designed pathway towards answers by means of an exhaustive catalogue of data sources and peer-reviewed information with relevance to the user question. Thus, MICA enables the user to explore data, acquire information and build up knowledge, rather than being given narrow, pre-formulated answers. The MICA Platform endeavours to cater for professional as well as general public stakeholders.

MICA développe la Plateforme européenne intégrée et intelligente consacrée aux matières premières, avec une interface innovante et conviviale. La plateforme fournit à l'utilisateur final une interface de visualisation qui guide l'utilisateur vers une formule "recette" permettant de trouver une réponse à toute question spécifique liée aux matières premières minérales. Ceci est différent des approches habituelles pour lesquelles une base de données ne répond qu'à des questions pré-formulées : MICA offre une approche de type expert avec, par l'intermédiaire d'un catalogue exhaustif de sources de données et d'information vérifiée collégialement, des réponses pertinentes aux questions posées par l'utilisateur. MICA permet donc à l'utilisateur d'étudier les données, d'acquérir une information qui nourrit la connaissance plutôt que de recevoir des réponses étroites et pré-formulées. La Plateforme MICA s'efforce de faire face aux exigences des professionnels comme des parties prenantes du secteur public.

MICA desarrolla la Plataforma Europea de Capacidad Inteligente de Materias Primas con una interfaz innovadora y sencilla. La plataforma proporciona al usuario final una interfaz de visualización que le orienta a una 'receta' sobre cómo encontrar respuestas a preguntas particulares relacionadas con materias primas minerales. Esto es diferente de los enfoques habituales, donde una base de datos proporciona únicamente respuestas a preguntas pre-formuladas: MICA ofrece un camino hacia las respuestas diseñado por expertos, mediante un catálogo exhaustivo de fuentes de datos e información relevante, revisada y contrastada, responde a la pregunta del usuario. Por lo tanto, MICA le permite al usuario explorar datos, adquirir información y acumular conocimiento, en lugar de recibir respuestas ceñidas y preformuladas. La Plataforma MICA tiene el objetivo de servir tanto a los profesionales como al público en general.

Introduction

This paper aims to outline the Mineral Intelligence Capacity Analysis (MICA) project for developing the European Union-Raw Materials Intelligence Capacity Platform (EU-RMICP). Mineral raw materials are fundamental to Europe's economy and further development. The MICA project represents a response to previous raw material initiatives (COM(2008)699¹, the "Report on criti-

¹ COM(2008)699 final. "On the Implementation of the Raw Materials Initiative", Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council, {SEC(2008)2741}, 04.11.2008, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52008DC0699>

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Figure 1: Outline of the MICA project structure.

Figure 2. Ninety stakeholders mapped to six stakeholder groups. Types of treatment: surveys (in bold), stakeholder workshop (underlined) and interviews (in italics). Indirect appraisal in the surveys is marked with an asterisk (*).

cal raw materials for the EU” (EC, 2010²; 2014³), COM(2011)21⁴, COM(2011)25⁵, as well as COM(2012)82⁶). Various projects

2 EC (2010) “Critical Raw Materials for the EU. Report of the Ad-Hoc Working Group on Defining Critical Raw Materials”, https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/eip-raw-materials/en/system/files/ged/79%20report-b_en.pdf, accessed 12.09.17.

3 EC (2014) “Report on the Critical Raw Materials for the EU. Report of the Ad Hoc Working Group on Defining Critical Raw Materials”, http://www.catalysiscluster.eu/wp/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/2014_Critical-raw-materials-for-the-EU-2014.pdf, accessed 12.09.17.

4 COM(2011)21 final. “A resource-efficient Europe – Flagship initiative under the Europe 2020 Strategy”, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, 26.1.2011, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0021>

5 COM (2011)25 final. “Tackling the challenges in commodity markets and on raw materials”, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, 2.2.2011, [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/meetdocs/2009_2014/documents/com/com_com\(2011\)0025_com_com\(2011\)0025_en.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/meetdocs/2009_2014/documents/com/com_com(2011)0025_com_com(2011)0025_en.pdf)

6 COM (2012)82 final. “Making raw materials available for Europe’s future well-being. Pro-

related to mineral raw materials, all of which contribute towards the development of the EU-RMICP and the EU-RMIS, have been funded in EU Framework Programmes as a result of this increased awareness, notably ProMine, EuroGeoSource, EURare, Minventory, Minerals4EU, ProSUM, I²Mine,

posal for a European Innovation Partnership on Raw Materials (EIP-RM)”, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, 29.2.2012, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/procedure/EN/201383>

Of all project partners, 16 partners are direct beneficiaries - namely the Geological Surveys of the UK (BGS), Germany (BGR), France (BRGM), Slovenia (GeoZS), Denmark (GEUS), Finland (GTK), as well as the European Federation of Geologists (EFG), EuroGeoSurveys (EGS), and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission, alongside Fraunhofer-ISI, the La Palma Research Centre (LPRC), Minpol GmbH, the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), University College London (UCL), Joseph Fournier University, Grenoble (UJF) and the University of Leiden’s Institute of Environmental Sciences (UL-CML). Another 15 linked third parties support the project, namely the Geological Surveys of Albania (AGS), Romania (GIR), Belgium (GSB), Cyprus (GSD), Ireland (GSI), Croatia (HGI-CGS), Institute of Geology and Mineral Exploration (IGME-Greece), Spain - the Institute of Geology and Mineral Exploration (IGME), the Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale (ISPRA, Italy), the Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia I.P. (LNEG, Portugal), and geological research organisations in Hungary (MBFSZ), Norway (NGU), Poland (PGI-NRI), Sweden (SGU) and Switzerland (Swisstopo).

EO-Miners, MINATURA2020 and others, and most recently the Knowledge and Innovation Community, EIT KIC Raw Materials was set up. MICA aims to synthesise the outcomes of previous projects and other initiatives into a stakeholder-tailored service – the “European Raw Materials Intelligence Capacity Platform” (EU-RMICP).

Project structure

MICA has a total project duration of 26 months (1 December 2015 to 31 January 2018) and a budget of EUR 2 million. A

total of 31 partners are working on the project (see box, previous page). The project is structured into seven work packages (WP) that are interwoven and feed into each other (Figure 1). The project management is undertaken in WP1 (led by GEUS); WP2 (led by Fraunhofer-ISI) identifies and defines stakeholder groups and their Raw Material Intelligence (RMI) requirements; WP3 (led by BGS) consolidates relevant data on primary and secondary raw materials; WP4 (led by UL-CML) determines appropriate methods and tools to satisfy stakeholder RMI requirements; WP5 (led by Minpol) investigates RMI-options for European mineral policy development; WP6 (led by BRGM) develops the EU-RMICP integrating information on data and methods/tools with a user interface capable of satisfying stakeholder needs; and WP7 (led by EGS) disseminates the project's results.

Stakeholder identification and stakeholder needs

As of today, a range of outputs ('deliverables') have been produced in MICA, as summarised below. A systematic inventory was undertaken that mapped 90 stakeholder groups (Erdmann *et al.*, 2016) according to three criteria legitimacy, power, and urgency of their issues (see Figure 2). The so-called 'definitive' stakeholders include, among others, those formally involved in the MICA project such as the geological surveys, public research institutes, universities, research and technology organisations, as well as intelligence institutes, professional organisations, industry (mining and extraction, production, recycling and material recovery, etc.), innovation initiatives, project management agencies, and ministries (economic affairs, education and research). 'Dominant' and 'dependent' stakeholders were considered in the comprehensive survey of raw material information needs. The manufacturing industry and governments represent dominant stakeholders. Business sectors that could potentially be affected by minerals RMI, such as e.g. the tourism industry or the bio-based industry, as well as civil society organisations e.g. environmental NGOs and human rights NGOs, are examples of dependent stakeholders.

MICA provided an *empirical appraisal of RMI needs of stakeholders* (Erdmann *et al.*, 2017) through three online surveys: one was conducted by EuroGeoSurveys reaching almost two thirds of its member geological surveys, another one by EFG to enhance the knowledge and understanding of raw material information needs of professional

Figure 3: The multidimensional ontology to support the DDG.

Figure 4: Domains used by the MICA ontology.

geologists as potential users of EU-RMICP, and a third industry survey reached out to strategic management of industry associations, covering large parts of the material supply chain from raw materials processing to recycling. A stakeholder workshop and 20 interviews with representatives from NGOs and industry, EU agencies, minis-

tries, cities, finance, education, and consumers were also conducted. The outcome of these surveys, the stakeholder workshop and interviews were condensed into a map of stakeholder needs in RMI that facilitated the finalisation of the 'MICA ontology', which is tailored towards the identified stakeholder topics of interest.

The ontology

In MICA, the *Main Multi-dimensional Ontology* represents the domain of questions end users may have about mineral resources/raw materials, see *Figure 3* (Cassard *et al.*, 2016). It is used for supporting a *Dynamic Decision Graph (DDG)* which allows the end users to navigate and visualise the MICA database content and the relationships between the different techniques, and to search for the most appropriate method(s) and tool(s) to use for resolving the user query (Cassard *et al.*, 2016). Depending on the users' preference or skills, a more or less 'visualised' and 'assisted' approach to their research is supported.

The ontology consists of seven domains, as presented in *Figure 4*, with about 300 concepts and sub-concepts (Cassard *et al.*, 2016). The main ontology and transversal 'generic' ontologies were developed collaboratively and interactively within the project, based on a survey performed by WP2 during the project kick-off meeting and drawing on experts from the project. To ensure that the main ontology represents end user (e.g., politicians, representatives of the EC, from governmental agencies, NGOs, academia and the general public) expectations or questions, it was informed by surveys undertaken in WP2, 3, 4 and 5, and thus its perimeter and depth/granularity improved. The main ontology is accompanied by three transversal, more 'generic' ontologies covering 'Value/Supply chains', 'Space/Time', and 'Commodities' that allow the end user to specify some fundamental 'search' parameters in order to speed up the discovery of the answer: where in the supply chain, which commodities, and where geographically (i.e., EU level, national level) and when (past/present/future).

Raw materials data inventory

Data and information are the foundation of any decision-making process, as they enable the creation of knowledge and intelligence and therefore are essential to the knowledge management system (EU-RMICP) that MICA develops. The 'Data – Information – Knowledge – Intelligence' (DIKI) hierarchy shown in *Figure 5* represents a conceptual framework for defining the terms and describing the levels of interpretation and analysis needed to move from data to intelligence. RMI depends very much on asking the right questions, and having the right underlying knowledge to act and move forward with decision-making. Although data, information, knowledge and intelligence are presented in a hierar-

Figure 5: From data to intelligence.

Figure 6: The fields of the metadata template used in MICA.

chical order, in reality iterative processes operate throughout the process to enable movement from the lowest level of the pyramid to the top.

MICA delivers an inventory of raw materials data, which consists of approximately 408 metadata records that give descriptive information on datasets. The development of the metadata structure and template, as well as the final inventory, the relationships between data and methods, and work undertaken on data uncertainty are described in the WP3 deliverables (see Petavratzi *et al.*, 2016; Petavratzi and Brown, 2017). The data inventory communicates with the EU-RMICP and therefore users can gain access to data tailored to their needs through the platform by navigating to topics of interest. An online data portal will also be available (<http://metadata.mica-project.eu/>), which includes metadata information about various datasets and inventories (e.g. geoportals, life cycle analysis databases), contextual information (e.g.

reports), articles from scientific journals, legal documents, maps and projects, among others. The metadata template (*Figure 6*) is based on ISO 19115 (2014) and is aligned with the INSPIRE Directive requirements and implementing rules for metadata (EC-JRC, 2013).

(In)visible guidance of users by experts

Based on the stakeholder needs elucidated in WP2 and expert opinions, mineral raw materials relevant knowledge is condensed into documents, the so-called 'FactSheets' and 'DocSheets'. These will be the end point at which a user query will arrive and will provide the user with essential supporting information, data and knowledge. These FactSheets/DocSheets cover a variety of methods by which RMI can be gathered as well as topics of interest aligned to identified stakeholder needs.

WP4 workshop "Methods and Tools for Raw Materials Intelligence" MICA workshop 27 September 2016
 Mapping research questions to methods and tools

	Methods to identify and assess geological and anthropogenic (urban) stocks					Methods to assess society's metabolism and its environmental impacts					Methods to assess the economic aspects of the use of resources					Methods to forecast or estimate future use of resources							
	Geological mapping	Remote sensing	Geochemical analysis	Ground investigation	Resource estimation	Material flow accounting	Material flow modelling	Life cycle assessment	Environmentally extended Input-Output Analysis	Risk Assessment	Footprinting	Cost Benefit Analysis	Life cycle costing	Input-output analysis	Criticality assessment	Econometrics	General Equilibrium Modelling	Bottom up forecasting	Top-down forecasting	Backcasting	horizon scanning	tech watchy/best practice	scenario storylines
1. What is the estimated size of resources (economic, reserve base, ultimate earth crust) over the past 50 years and where are they located?						●						●											
2. What is the estimated size of resources in urban stocks (i.e. stocks-in-use) over the past 50 years and where are they located?	●	●									●	●	●										
3. What was the extraction of raw materials over the past 50 years and where were they extracted?																							

Figure 7: Excerpt from contribution of methods to answering stakeholder questions.

Methods for data use

The *FactSheets of methods* for RMI are essential to put data into context within the EU-RMICP (van der Voet *et al.*, 2016a). They address methods to identify and assess geological and anthropogenic (urban) stocks (including geological mapping methods also applicable to secondary stocks e.g. landfills or underground hibernating stocks). The methods comprise two categories: a) to account for stocks in use, and b) to follow them through society together with their impacts, e.g. Material Flow Analysis (MFA); Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) within the context of Life Cycle Sustainability Analysis for the life-cycle of materials, environmental footprinting, economic aspects of resource use (Cost Benefit Analysis; Econometric and Computable General Equilibrium models; criticality assessment), as well as scenario analysis for future resource use. These methods have been assessed as to their usefulness to help answer stakeholders' questions; see excerpt from the exercise in Figure 7 (van der Voet *et al.*, 2016b).

In addition, more than 100 other *FactSheets and DocSheets* on identified topics are being elaborated by project collaborators with particular knowledge and expertise. These sheets undergo a peer-review process and are then revised. The documents therefore represent a unique and qualified source of information in EU-RMICP.

The so-called *FlowSheets* are in essence recipes that come into play upon specific queries by the end user and prescribe the flow of data and information, e.g., which *DocSheets/FactSheets* and which datasets should be used, following a certain order, to solve the query of the end user. The content

Figure 8: Mechanisms of minerals policy framework. Source: Tiess, 2011, adapted 2017.

of the *FlowSheets* will be visible to the end user and reflects expert knowledge that was at play when these were designed.

Policy relevance and foresight

MICA also delivered a discussion and summary of RMI tools and methods, including an assessment of the EU Raw Material Initiative, which provides a general framework for a mineral policy but lacks systematic RMI in the EU (Falck *et al.*, 2016). A multi-dimensional matrix serves to outline the various RMI dimensions, the main dimensions being the minerals policy frameworks and their governing principles at national, European, and global level, stakeholder needs and expectations (e.g., the mechanisms of minerals policy frameworks) (see Figure 7), and methods and strategies to predict future development in the use, demand, and supply of minerals.

Furthermore, a *foresight logframe* was elaborated (Konrat Martins and Bodo, 2016) that reviews international foresight case studies based on an inventory structured into three classes: quantitative, macro-environmental, and a methods-combination-suitability matrix. The quantitative classification addresses measurable aspects, such as the number of people and institutions involved. The macro-environmental classification outlines large-scale environmental factors that were the object of study, while the matrix of methods, combinations and suitability reviews the methods observed in the study.

Outreach

The MICA *graphical identity* is used in *promotion material* distributed at numerous events including the EGS MREG meeting 2015, the 7th session of the UNECE Expert

Group of Resource Classification, and the World Circular Economy Forum 2017, in accordance with its *communication strategy and dissemination plans* (Delfini *et al.*, 2016). Information about MICA's progress can be obtained also via various social media (Delfini, 2017): Twitter ([@micaproject2015](https://twitter.com/micaproject2015)), LinkedIn (www.linkedin.com/company/7957049/), and Facebook (www.facebook.com/micaproject2015). News and deliverables are available from the MICA project website: www.mica-project.eu.

Conclusions

By project completion in January 2018, a raw materials data and methods strategy and a conceptual framework for the transformation of data into knowledge will have been delivered with the EU-RMICP. The ambition of the EU-RMICIP is to help stakeholders find answers to raw materials related questions, even if they have no experience and knowledge of using one of the spatial geoportals, raw materials databases, or other related tools and methods. It

is hoped that this will help stakeholders to better understand how data, methods and raw materials-related decisions will impact their daily life.

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